

The Use of Collaborative Learning Models to Improve Students' Ability to Communicate in English for Elementary Schools

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Abstract: *English language learning at the elementary school level is a crucial foundation for building communication skills from an early age, especially in the face of global competition that requires students to be active in English. However, teaching practices in elementary schools still largely use lecture and memorization methods that do not provide many opportunities for students to practice speaking practically. Given this situation, collaborative learning approaches are considered effective because they provide space for social interaction among students and facilitate the practical and meaningful use of English in an engaging environment. The literature review in this article refers to sources that discuss the concept of collaborative learning, its advantages in language teaching, and its success in improving students' communication skills in accordance with their psychological development stages. Several previous studies have shown that collaborative activities such as group discussions, presentations, role-playing, and project assignments can consistently improve students' speaking fluency, confidence, pronunciation, and vocabulary. The research method applied is a literature review by collecting data from relevant domestic and foreign journals, especially research related to English language teaching in elementary schools. The analysis was carried out through an assessment of the similarity of findings, context variations, and implementation approaches.*

Keywords: collaborative, communication, speaking, interaction, learning

INTRODUCTION

English has developed into the primary means of communication in the international world thanks to its function as a global language and the language of technology. With the rapid pace of globalization and technological advances, there is no doubt that proficiency in English is one of the important factors for obtaining better career opportunities and achieving success in the future (Ichda Faridatuunnisa, 2020). In addition, communicating in English opens doors for individuals to obtain information from various parts of the world, keep up with scientific developments, and adapt to increasingly rapid global changes. In the field of education, this

highlights the need to strengthen language skills from an early age in order to prepare the younger generation to face the challenges of an increasingly integrated world.

English language teaching at the elementary school level aims to introduce students to languages other than their native language, which they can use in their daily lives. Therefore, this language should be taught through activities that are suitable for children. For example, learning simple vocabulary and sentences about things around them, or through activities such as drawing, singing, playing, and storytelling, so that the learning process feels more natural and enjoyable (Nuroh, 2016). This approach not only makes learning more interesting, but also helps students form a solid language foundation through practical experience.

The collaborative learning model is currently a major focus for educators. This model emphasizes interaction among students and cooperation in groups, which can increase student participation in the learning process. In elementary schools, where enjoyable and inclusive learning experiences are crucial, collaborative methods offer an appropriate and efficient approach (Apriliani et al., 2024). Through discussion and cooperation, students can support each other and build knowledge together. Collaborative learning can also encourage student participation in the learning process and help increase their enthusiasm for learning (Darmawan & Pujiastuti, 2023). This shows that the application of a collaborative model in English teaching can further enrich the learning atmosphere in elementary schools.

PROBLEM STATEMENT

This work concludes the issue of approaches to deeply understanding the importance of applying collaborative learning models to improve the communication skills of elementary school students in English. This issue arises from the condition of English teaching in elementary schools, which still emphasizes memorization and writing exercises, thus not providing adequate opportunities for students to actively practice speaking. In addition, many students lack confidence when using English, so learning strategies that encourage social interaction and cooperation among students are needed, in accordance with the characteristics of elementary school children's learning. At the same time, it is necessary to evaluate how collaborative learning models can produce meaningful learning experiences and support students' courage to communicate. Thus, this work aims to

answer the main issue of how the application of collaborative learning models can improve students' communication skills in English at the elementary school level.

METHOD

The approach used in writing this article is the Literature Review research method. This method involves collecting and assessing data obtained by previous researchers, which can usually be found in articles, journals, or books. This process is in line with the concept of literature review, which involves reviewing, assessing, and combining various theories and findings from previous studies related to the topic being researched. (Wulandar et al., 2025). The collaborative learning model is a method in which learners collaborate in small groups to discuss, exchange ideas, and complete tasks collectively. This approach is applied because it has been proven to increase learning engagement, confidence, and students' speaking skills, as revealed in research. (Haryadi, 2024), (Nuroh, 2016). The participants were elementary school students, with teachers acting as learning facilitators (Husain, n.d.) , (Idan I. Pakaya & Duprisna Ibrahim, 2019). The implementation took place in both formal and informal classrooms, enabling effective communication and social interaction(Muslimin & Stela Ramadhani Khalashnikov, 2025). The activity was conducted during English language learning sessions, particularly during group activities(Hastomo et al., 2022). The application was carried out by dividing participants into groups, conducting discussions, role-playing, delivering presentations, and providing feedback, so that the learning process became interactive, focused, and student-oriented.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In his work, (Haryadi, 2024)states that collaborative learning is a personal outlook on life, not just a method used in the classroom. He argues that collaboration is a method of interaction that makes cooperation the main foundation for achieving common goals. In addition, cooperation is considered a method of interaction that emphasizes respect for the abilities and contributions of each individual in the group. He states that collaborative learning can improve communication skills, critical thinking skills, and motivate students to learn. When students work in groups, they not only gain knowledge from the teacher, but also from their friends.

The following is the syntax and examples of the application of collaborative learning in school learning:

NO	Syntax	Examples of application in learning
1.	Orientation & Presentation of Objectives	The teacher explains the topic "self-introduction expressions (greetings and introductions)" along with the objectives to be achieved. In addition, the teacher provides guidelines for group work. The teacher also gives examples of simple expressions, such as "Hello," "My name is...," and "I am ... years old." Furthermore, the teacher explains that in the next activity, students will collaborate in groups to compose an introductory dialogue.
2.	Group Division & Tasks	The teacher divided the students into small groups consisting of 4 to 6 students. Next, the teacher gave tasks or problems to be solved collaboratively.
3.	Idea Development (Discussion)	Students discuss in groups, exchange opinions, seek solutions, and share information and learning resources.
4.	Compiling the Results of Collaboration	The group compiles ideas that become answers/works (e.g., dialogues, presentations, posters, or discussion results).
5.	Group Presentation	Group representatives present their discussion results in front of the class. Other groups provide feedback.

(Nuroh, 2016) states that the collaborative approach places students as active learners who are able to organize, make decisions, and solve problems independently in groups. In the context of English language learning in elementary schools, this approach provides opportunities for students to engage in direct language experiences, such as speaking, listening, discussing, and collaborating on authentic communicative tasks. It also emphasizes that collaborative learning can provide opportunities for students to develop their functional communication skills, as they practice using language in real contexts, rather than just learning separate language forms.

These findings are in line with the study presented by (Setiawati & Nur, 2025) , which reveals that the use of collaborative learning models actually improves the speaking skills of elementary school students, particularly in terms of fluency, vocabulary, pronunciation, content, and grammar. The study also emphasizes that collaborative activities such as small group discussions, pair work, role-playing, and group presentations provide opportunities for students to practice English repeatedly, thereby developing their verbal communication skills more quickly. These activities allow students to give each other feedback, correct mistakes, and discuss appropriate language use, while building confidence when speaking.

The findings (Hastomo et al., 2022) of the study " show that the application of collaborative learning can effectively improve students' speaking skills through discussions, group work, and targeted communicative activities, because this strategy creates an interactive classroom where students are more confident, dare to express their opinions, and actively use English. The improvement in speaking skills was evident through classroom observations and a comparison of pre-test and post-test scores, which showed significant progress in terms of fluency, pronunciation, vocabulary mastery, and students' courage to speak. This is in line with the argument in this article that the collaborative learning model provides meaningful opportunities for students from elementary school to practice English directly, not just memorizing theory, but getting used to communicating through fun and structured social interactions. Thus, collaborative learning is an effective approach to developing students' oral communication skills and can be implemented well in English language learning in elementary schools.

In addition, (Maro, 2016)The 2013 curriculum adopts various approaches such as the scientific method, exploration through investigation, problem-focused instruction, and project-based learning, all of which require group collaboration. These techniques foster deep analytical skills through activities such as observation, questioning, rational thinking, practical testing, and working together to overcome obstacles or complete tasks. These analytical skills are strongly linked to verbal competence, as students must express their opinions, provide logical evidence, evaluate information, and respond to their peers' ideas through conversation. Thus, the educational strategies in the 2013 Curriculum also reinforce the benefits of collaborative learning to improve the communication skills of elementary school students in English.

CONCLUSION

Based on the literature review and analysis conducted in this article, the implementation of a collaborative learning approach has proven to be effective in improving the speaking skills of elementary school students in English. Through group interaction activities, intensive discussions, and exercises that emphasize communication, students can more actively utilize English in practical situations. As a result, there is a significant improvement in speaking fluency, vocabulary expansion, pronunciation improvement, and increased confidence. This approach allows students to apply language in everyday contexts, rather than just memorizing theory. Thus, collaborative learning has high potential to produce meaningful learning experiences and encourage active participation at the elementary school level.

In addition, this collaborative method is very suitable for elementary school children, who need an engaging learning environment and meaningful activities. This strategy provides opportunities for students to interact socially, collaborate in teams, exchange ideas, and solve challenges together. This process not only strengthens communication skills, but also supports the development of their courage to express their views in English. Through repeated practice, students can experience real progress in terms of fluency and confidence when using the language.

In addition, the implementation of this collaborative learning model is very much in line with the requirements of the 2013 Curriculum, which emphasizes active learning, analytical thinking skills, and team collaboration. The application of methods such as class debates, role-playing, joint presentations, or light project assignments helps students become more focused, organized, and fully immersed in learning activities. Here, the role of educators is crucial, namely to develop systematic instructional stages so that educational goals can be optimally achieved. Ultimately, this collaborative approach not only improves verbal skills but also encourages the growth of interpersonal skills, self-confidence, and resilience in students in dealing with communication barriers in the future. Most importantly, educators must monitor interactions within the group to ensure that every student has equal opportunities and that no one is left behind.

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